

EFFECTIVENESS OF KINESIOTHERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH LUMBOSACRAL RADICULOPATHY

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the effectiveness of kinesiotherapy in the treatment of lumbosacral radiculopathy.

Keywords: kinesiotherapy, physical rehabilitation, osteochondrosis, therapeutic physical culture.

Formulation of the problem.

The article presents the results of a study on the effectiveness of kinesiotherapy in treating patients with lumbosacral radiculopathy. The research findings indicate that the predominant syndrome in patients with radiculopathy was pain syndrome.

Despite a shortage of concise epidemiological data in the literature, most reports roughly estimate the prevalence of lumbosacral radiculopathy among patients at 3% to 5%. While the occurrence rate of back pain ranges from 13% to 31%, the frequency of radicular symptoms in patients with back pain varies from 12% to 40%. In the workforce, back pain ranks as the second most common cause of work absenteeism after upper respiratory infections. Approximately 25 million people miss one or more workdays due to back pain, and over five million become disabled as a result. Patients with chronic back pain account for 80% to 90% of all healthcare expenditures.

Pain in the lower back, especially in the lumbar region, is one of the most common complaints associated with musculoskeletal issues. Its high prevalence poses significant challenges for those affected. This pain can become chronic, limiting a person's ability to lead a normal life, significantly impairing their quality of life, and leading to disability. Particularly in developed countries, where the economic losses from this condition amount to millions of dollars annually. Various epidemiological studies have shown that lower back pain occurs in 60% to 90% of cases throughout one's lifetime.

One of the most common forms of lower back pain is radiculopathy, also known as leg pain associated with the lumbar spine. Radiculopathy symptoms are more pronounced and persistent compared to non-specific lower back pain without nerve root involvement.

Vertebrogenic lumbar radiculopathy (VLR) is a term that refers to a pain syndrome caused by compression or irritation of nerve roots in the lumbar spine. This compression can be triggered by intervertebral disc herniation, vertebral degeneration, and narrowing of the intervertebral foramen. Symptoms of VLR include lower back pain that may radiate to the lower extremities along corresponding dermatomes, numbness, weakness, and loss of reflexes. Clinical manifestations can range from temporary radicular pain to persistent, disabling motor deficits.

The effectiveness of various kinesiotherapy methods in treating patients with lumbar radiculopathy re-

mains insufficiently researched. According to the analysis of literature data [1, 2], physiotherapeutic methods, including kinesiotherapy, are recognized as effective components of rehabilitation in the treatment of various spinal disorders.

The pathogenesis of lumbosacral radiculopathy involves the affliction of nerve roots emerging from the lumbar-sacral spine. Various factors and mechanisms may contribute to the pathogenesis of radiculopathy. Key pathogenetic aspects of this condition include:

- Compression of nerve roots: Radiculopathy often arises due to compression or constriction of nerve roots caused by deformation of intervertebral discs, osteophytes (bony outgrowths) on vertebrae, or other anomalies in the vertebral column [3].

- Pain sensations: Compression of nerve roots leads to irritation of nerve fibers, causing sharp pain along the corresponding nerve root. This pain can be acute and intense, localized in the back, buttocks, thigh, and leg.

- Inflammatory process: Compression of nerve roots can trigger an inflammatory response in surrounding tissues, leading to swelling, pain, and irritation of nerve structures.

- Disk rupture: In some cases, radiculopathy may result from the rupture of intervertebral discs, causing the release of gel-like disc material and irritation of nerve roots.

- Degenerative changes: Age-related and degenerative changes in the vertebral column can lead to compression of nerve roots due to alterations in the spinal column structure, such as disc herniation, spondylosis, spondyloarthritis, and others.

- Mechanical injuries: Traumatic damage to the vertebral column can lead to radiculopathy if it results in the compression of nerve roots.

Radiculopathy is a medical condition characterized by the compression or irritation of one or multiple nerve roots in the spine. It typically presents with pain, weakness, numbness, or tingling that radiates along the path of the affected nerve. Radiculopathy can occur at various levels of the spine and is classified based on its location and underlying cause. Here are some common classifications of radiculopathy:

- Cervical radiculopathy: Affects the nerve roots in the neck region.

- Thoracic radiculopathy: Involves nerve root compression in the mid-back region.

- Lumbar radiculopathy: Occurs when nerve roots in the lower back are affected.

Each type may have distinct causes and symptoms associated with the specific area of the spine involved.

Cervical radiculopathy: It occurs when there is compression or irritation of nerve roots in the cervical (neck) section of the spine. Typically, it is accompanied by symptoms in the neck, shoulder, arm, and hand. Common causes include disc herniation, bone spurs, or degenerative changes in the cervical spine.

Thoracic radiculopathy: Radiculopathy in the thoracic (mid-back) region is less common than in the cervical or lumbar regions. It may result from conditions such as disc herniation, trauma, or a tumor affecting the roots of thoracic nerves. Symptoms may include pain or numbness in the chest, ribs, or upper abdomen.

Diagnosing lumbar radiculopathy requires a comprehensive approach and may involve the following methods:

- Medical examination and medical history: Conducting an interview with the patient to gather information about symptoms, duration and nature of pain, as well as other potential factors contributing to the symptoms.

Materials and Methods:

The study included 25 patients aged 35 to 64 years. The majority of patients had a long-standing history of lumbar radiculopathy. In 13 (52%) patients, the condition persisted for more than 5 years.

Most patients at the time of examination experienced frequent exacerbations lasting 3-6 months. Out of 25 patients, 14 (56%) had additional comorbidities (Figure 3.1.3). Specifically, 7 individuals (28%) had ischemic heart disease (IHD), 9 (36%) had arterial hypertension (AH), 2 (8%) were diagnosed with degenerative osteoarthritis (DOA), 4 (16%) had gastrointestinal issues (GIT), and 5 (20%) suffered from obesity (OB). Vegetovascular dystonia (VVD) affected 7 (28%) patients. These comorbidities complicated the course of lumbar radiculopathy and made treatment choices more challenging.

Research methods:

As part of the qualification work, safety standards for patients were observed, their rights and dignity were preserved in accordance with the basic principles of GCP, the Convention of the Council of Europe on Human Rights and Biomedicine (from 04.04.1977), the Helsinki Declaration of the World Medical Association on the ethical principles of conducting scientific medical research with human participation (1964-2000) and the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 281 dated November 1, 2000. All participants were fully informed about the purpose of the study and gave written consent to their participation in it.

25 patients diagnosed with radiculopathy of the lumbosacral spine were included in the study. The patients were divided into two groups. The 1st group, which served as a comparison, was engaged in the generally accepted method of rehabilitation for radiculopathy of the lumbosacral spine, which included LH, therapeutic massage, and in the 2nd group, kinesiotherapy was applied according to the improved "Motion Puzzle" program.

The criteria for including patients in the study were:

- patients diagnosed with radiculopathy of the lumbosacral spine;
- age from 35 to 65 years;
- pain syndrome in the lumbar spine, vertebrogenic etiology of the process;
- degree of symptoms at the same level.

Exclusion criteria:

- age over 65 years;
- the presence of an acute stage of the disease
- patients with acute pain;
- disc herniations;
- pregnancy;
- spine injuries;
- gout
- oncological diseases;
- congenital anomalies of spine development;
- Bekhterev's disease;
- refusal to participate in the study;
- bad effect of the proposed rehabilitation method;
- spinal injuries and other injuries;
- participation in another study.

Research design:

- on the first day, criteria were evaluated to determine who can participate in the study and who should be excluded;

- conduct an interview with each patient, discuss his possible participation in the study and obtain informed consent;

- all patients were prescribed a standard examination and protocol drug treatment;

- after signing the informed consent, they were randomly divided into groups.

The following examinations were carried out: completion of the VASH scale - to assess the intensity of pain syndrome in the case of radiculopathy of the lumbosacral spine, completion of the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) questionnaire - to assess the quality of life and adaptation to everyday life, recovery index (IR) - to assess the degree of recovery after rehabilitation and determination of the Roland-Maurice index to assess the degree of limitations associated with spinal disease. Kinesiotherapy was prescribed according to the "movement puzzle" method in the 2nd group, and the 1st group according to the standard method.

- re-examination in order to determine the effectiveness and safety of the treatment was carried out after 1 month. after the start of rehabilitation.

The Visual Analog Scale (VAS) is an effective tool for measuring pain intensity, a leading symptom in radiculopathy. Application techniques of VAS:

1. Preparation of materials:

- Ensure the availability of a large sheet of paper or ruler.

- Have a scale (usually from 0 to 10) for assessing pain intensity.

The use of VAS allows obtaining quantitative data on pain, facilitating the assessment of treatment effectiveness, rehabilitation, and contributing to informed medical decision-making.

The study showed that before treatment, the average pain level according to the VAS scale in patients of both groups did not differ significantly. However, after

a month of treatment, the effect was significant, especially in the 2nd group, where a statistically significant decrease in pain level was observed compared to the 1st group.

At the beginning of treatment, according to the ODI questionnaire, patients had problems with quality of life, with an average functional capacity of 51 ± 0.7 points. Before treatment, the groups were similar on ODI survey scores.

After a month of rehabilitation, the 1st group almost did not change its indicators (50.5 ± 2.1 to 47.1 ± 1.3 points, $p > 0.05$), while the 2nd group showed a significant improvement (52.2 ± 1.8 to 25.8 ± 1.1 points, $p < 0.05$). Differences between groups became statistically significant. In the 2nd group, the improvement was 49.4%, compared to only 7% in the 1st group. The use of kinesiotherapy according to the "Motion puzzle" program gave better results in the rehabilitation of patients with radiculopathy of the lumbosacral spine.

Patients with radiculopathy of the lumbosacral spine showed great limitations in daily activities, especially due to severe pain according to the Roland-Morris questionnaire (> 9 points). Before rehabilitation, all had a similar pain index, the average score was 15.9 ± 1.8 . The use of rehabilitation methods led to a decrease in pain, improvement in range of motion and muscle tone function. After one month of rehabilitation, the 2nd group showed a greater improvement (56.8% vs. 26.6% in the 1st group), which was statistically significant. The results of the Roland-Maurice questionnaire confirm the normalization of functions in the 2nd group, which emphasizes the effectiveness of the "Movement puzzle" program in kinesiotherapy.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the use of kinesiotherapy according to the "Motion Puzzle" program significantly improves the efficiency of rehabilitation of patients with radiculopathy of the lumbosacral spine.

Conclusions:

1. Examining scientific and medical sources reveals that lumbar radiculopathy is a serious condition accompanied by the involvement of spinal nerve roots. Key aspects of this condition include pain, paresthesia, and weakness in corresponding areas of the body. Its development is linked to degenerative changes, injuries, or congenital spinal abnormalities. Understanding these aspects contributes to improving the diagnosis and treatment of radiculopathy, enhancing the quality of life for patients.

2. In the 1st group, based on the VAS scale, pain intensity decreased by 12.8%, while in the 2nd group, it decreased by 71.6%. Kinesiotherapy using the "Movement Puzzle" program, applied to the 2nd group of patients with lumbar radiculopathy, demonstrated a statistically significant pain reduction compared to the 1st group ($p < 0.05$), which followed a standard methodology.

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